

BIOTECHNOLOGY IN SPACE - ENGINEERING FOOD PLANTS FOR PHARMACEUTICAL ADVANCEMENTS

BIOTECHNOLOGIE IM RAUM – ENTWICKLUNG VON LEBENSMITTELPFLANZEN FÜR PHARMAZEUTISCHE FORTSCHRITTE

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Abstract:

This article explores the cutting-edge intersection of biotechnology and space research, where genetic engineering and advanced technologies are redefining our approach to long-range spacecraft missions. At its core, the article delves into the concept of food plants engineered as pharmaceutical platforms, representing a groundbreaking solution to the challenges of space exploration. These genetically modified plants serve as bioreactors for drug production within spacecraft, offering a self-sustaining source of therapeutic compounds.

Biosensors play a pivotal role in this context, enabling real-time monitoring and analysis of biological information related to drug production, ensuring precision and control. Additionally, the integration of regenerative medicine strategies into pharmaceutical plant platforms enhances the well-being of astronauts during extended space missions, stimulating tissue repair and regeneration.

Genetic engineering techniques are at the forefront, optimizing plants for pharmaceutical production in the demanding space environment. Personalized genetic modifications further tailor these plants to individual astronaut needs, ensuring the production of drugs that align with specific physiological characteristics.

Advancements in DNA repair capabilities of genetically modified plants safeguard genomic stability in space environments. Metagenomics offers insights into the microbial ecosystems within spacecraft, aiding in the optimization of cultivation conditions and ecosystem interactions.

Neuroprosthetics enable real-time monitoring and control of plant health, contributing to adaptability in space habitats.

Genetically engineered microorganisms close the loop within spacecraft ecosystems, efficiently recycling nutrients and enhancing habitat stability. Closed cultivation systems optimize resource utilization, water efficiency, and waste management, ensuring a consistent supply of food and oxygen.

In summary, this interdisciplinary approach to space biotechnology promises a future where humans can thrive on extended journeys beyond Earth, with genetically modified plants serving as the cornerstone of sustainable space exploration.

Keywords: Space biotechnology, Genetic engineering, Pharmaceutical plant platforms, Biosensors, Regenerative medicine, DNA repair, Metagenomics, Neuroprosthetics, Genetically modified microorganisms, Closed cultivation systems.

Abstract:

Dieser Artikel untersucht die hochmoderne Schnittstelle zwischen Biotechnologie und Weltraumforschung, wo Gentechnik und fortschrittliche Technologien unseren Ansatz für Langstreckenmissionen von Raumfahrzeugen neu definieren. Im Kern befasst sich der Artikel mit dem Konzept von Nahrungsmittelpflanzen, die als pharmazeutische Plattformen konstruiert werden und eine bahnbrechende Lösung für die Herausforderungen der Weltraumforschung darstellen. Diese gentechnisch veränderten Pflanzen dienen als Bioreaktoren für die Arzneimittelproduktion in Raumfahrzeugen und bieten eine autarke Quelle für therapeutische Verbindungen.

Biosensoren spielen in diesem Zusammenhang eine zentrale Rolle. Sie ermöglichen die Echtzeitüberwachung und -analyse biologischer Informationen im Zusammenhang mit der Arzneimittelproduktion und gewährleisten so Präzision und Kontrolle. Darüber hinaus steigert die Integration regenerativer Medizinstrategien in pharmazeutische Anlagenplattformen das Wohlbefinden von Astronauten bei ausgedehnten Weltraummissionen und stimuliert die Gewebereparatur und -regeneration.

Im Vordergrund stehen gentechnische Techniken, die Anlagen für die pharmazeutische Produktion im anspruchsvollen Weltraumumfeld optimieren. Personalisierte genetische Veränderungen passen diese Pflanzen weiter an die Bedürfnisse der einzelnen Astronauten an und stellen so die Produktion von Medikamenten sicher, die auf spezifische physiologische Eigenschaften abgestimmt sind.

Fortschritte bei der DNA-Reparaturfähigkeit gentechnisch veränderter Pflanzen gewährleisten die genomische Stabilität in Weltraumumgebungen. Metagenomik bietet Einblicke in die mikrobiellen Ökosysteme in Raumfahrzeugen und hilft bei der Optimierung der Kultivierungsbedingungen und Ökosysteminteraktionen. Neuroprothetik ermöglicht die Überwachung und Kontrolle der Pflanzengesundheit in Echtzeit und trägt so zur Anpassungsfähigkeit in Weltraumlebensräumen bei.

Gentechnisch veränderte Mikroorganismen schließen den Kreislauf innerhalb der Ökosysteme von Raumfahrzeugen, indem sie Nährstoffe effizient recyceln und die Lebensraumstabilität verbessern. Geschlossene Anbausysteme optimieren die Ressourcennutzung, die Wassereffizienz und das Abfallmanagement und sorgen für eine gleichmäßige Versorgung mit Nahrungsmitteln und Sauerstoff.

Zusammenfassend lässt sich sagen, dass dieser interdisziplinäre Ansatz der Weltraumbiotechnologie eine Zukunft verspricht, in der Menschen auf ausgedehnten Reisen über die Erde hinaus erfolgreich sein können, wobei gentechnisch veränderte Pflanzen als Eckpfeiler einer nachhaltigen Weltraumforschung dienen.

Schlüsselwörter: Weltraumbiotechnologie, Gentechnik, pharmazeutische Pflanzenplattformen, Biosensoren, Regenerative Medizin, DNA-Reparatur, Metagenomik, Neuroprothetik, genetisch veränderte Mikroorganismen, geschlossene Kultivierungssysteme.

1. INTRODUCTION

The intersection of biotechnology and space exploration has ushered in a new era of innovation, where genetic engineering and cutting-edge technologies are revolutionizing our approach to long-range spacecraft missions. One of the most intriguing developments in this field involves the use of food plants engineered as pharmaceutical platforms. These plants, genetically modified to act as bioreactors for drug production within spacecraft, represent a groundbreaking solution to the challenges of space research.

In this context, biosensors have emerged as essential components, providing real-time monitoring and analysis of biological information related to drug production. This monitoring ensures precise control over the synthesis and release of therapeutic compounds, optimizing pharmaceutical plant platforms for space missions.

But it doesn't stop there; regenerative medicine has also found its place in space exploration, offering strategies to stimulate tissue repair and regeneration, vital for the well-being of astronauts during extended space missions. The integration of these regenerative medicine techniques into pharmaceutical plant platforms further enhances the sustainability and health of space habitats.

Genetic engineering takes center stage in the modification of plants for optimal pharmaceutical production in the harsh environment of space. These genetic modifications enhance the plants' metabolic pathways, ensuring efficient synthesis of specific pharmaceutical compounds, making them reliable and consistent bioreactors throughout the mission.

Moreover, personalized genetic modifications are implemented, tailoring the plants to accommodate the specific pharmaceutical needs of individual astronauts. This customization ensures that drugs and therapeutic agents are produced to match the unique physiological characteristics and medical requirements of each crew member.

Another significant advancement involves genetically modified food plants with DNA damage correction capabilities. These plants possess mechanisms for self-repairing DNA damage, ensuring genomic stability and functionality in the challenging space environment.

Metagenomics, a tool for studying genetic material directly from environmental samples in space habitats, allows for comprehensive analysis of microbial communities and genetic diversity. This knowledge aids in optimizing cultivation conditions and understanding the interactions between genetically modified plants and the microbial ecosystem.

Neuroprosthetics, artificial devices enhancing nervous system function, have applications in space research by interfacing with genetically modified plants for real-time monitoring and control of their DNA repair mechanisms and overall health.

Microorganisms, genetically modified to perform specific functions such as nutrient cycling and waste management, create closed-loop ecosystems within spacecraft, enhancing the sustainability of plant cultivation.

Closed cultivation systems are vital for long-range spacecraft missions, with genetically modified plants designed to thrive in these environments. These plants optimize resource utilization, water efficiency, and waste management, contributing to the self-sufficiency of space habitats.

2. DEVELOPMENT

Food plants engineered as pharmaceutical platforms represent a cutting-edge approach in space research, where genetic manipulation enables the production of drugs and therapeutic compounds. This technology leverages the genetic modification of edible plants to serve as bioreactors for pharmaceutical production within spacecraft. The integration of biosensors enhances the functionality of these plant-based platforms by allowing the real-time monitoring and analysis of biological information related to drug production.

Biosensors are essential components in the context of pharmaceutical plant platforms. These devices are designed to detect and analyze biological information, including the concentration of pharmaceutical compounds and other relevant biomarkers. Biosensors provide critical data for the optimization of drug production, ensuring precise control over the synthesis and release of therapeutic agents.

Regenerative medicine plays a complementary role in space exploration by leveraging the body's innate capacity to repair and regenerate tissues. This field aims to stimulate and enhance tissue regeneration, which is particularly important in the context of extended space missions where

astronauts may face challenges related to tissue damage and healing. Regenerative medicine strategies are integrated into the pharmaceutical plant platforms to support astronauts' health and well-being during space travel.

Genetic engineering techniques play a crucial role in modifying plants to optimize pharmaceutical production in the challenging environment of long-range spacecraft. These modifications enhance the plants' metabolic pathways, enabling efficient synthesis of specific pharmaceutical compounds. The technology has rapidly advanced, overcoming early-stage drawbacks such as the need for high protein expression levels and efficient downstream processing (Shanmugaraj et al., 2020). Metabolic engineering through transformation with *Agrobacterium* species and manipulation of plant metabolic signaling pathways has been extensively used to enhance the production of pharmaceutically valuable secondary metabolites in plants and plant in vitro systems (Marchev et al., 2020). Metabolic engineering has provided alternative production pathways for the synthesis of pharmaceuticals, fuels, and soft materials by redirecting carbon flux toward specific metabolites (Fan et al., 2018).

Plant genetic engineering technologies have shown substantial progress in the production of pharmaceutical products, making it a viable platform for recombinant biopharmaceutical production (Habibi et al., 2019). Furthermore, plants can efficiently produce a range of pharmaceuticals at low cost, making them an attractive option for pharmaceutical production (Chung et al., 2021). Loss of the peptidoglycan wall during the evolution of land plants is a significant irreversible step towards reducing plastid survival outside the plant cell (Daniell et al., 2021). Genetically encoded biosensors can significantly reduce the effort for strain optimization and evolution, empowering exploration of a larger cellular control and strain design space in plant metabolic engineering (Marsafari et al., 2020).

Existing methods to control genetic activities typically rely on chemical inducers, radio waves, and magnetic or light activation. However, metabolic engineering has provided alternative production pathways for the synthesis of pharmaceuticals, fuels, and soft materials by redirecting carbon flux toward specific metabolites (Pan et al., 2018). Plant metabolic engineering strategies have been studied extensively for the production of pharmaceutical terpenoids, providing theoretical support for plant metabolic engineering studies (Lu et al.,

2016). Among all meta-heuristics, genetic algorithms have extensive civil/construction engineering applications from structural optimization to scheduling (Uysal et al., 2021).

Pharmaceutical production capability hardwired into the genome of the plant through nuclear or plastid engineering has been proposed, highlighting the potential of molecular pharming to support human life on the Moon, Mars, and beyond (McNulty et al., 2020). When expanding to produce a large space of desirable chemicals, the current strain engineering approach will become increasingly laborious and expensive (Wilbanks et al., 2017). The mutual regulation of metabolic flow between pathways is common in plants, indicating the potential for enhancing biosynthetic pathways through metabolic engineering (Chen et al., 2021).

In addition to protein synthesis, plants utilize tyrosine to produce a diverse array of specialized metabolites, which also have important applications as pharmaceuticals. Therefore, redirecting primary metabolism to boost the production of tyrosine-derived specialized metabolites in planta is a promising approach (Timoneda et al., 2018). Potent transient expression systems achieve production yields at levels of grams per kilogram of plant tissue, making plant-based biopharmaceutical engineering a highly efficient platform (Eidenberger et al., 2023). The potential provided by the production of recombinant pharmaceutical proteins in plants for therapeutic applications was realized much later than in bacterial, yeast, and animal systems (Ayan et al., 2022).

Metabolic engineering has proved invaluable for the production of pharmaceuticals, particularly multimeric proteins such as antibodies, and complex technical proteins such as collagen and spider silk (Tschofen et al., 2016). The shikimic acid pathway has different metabolic branches in different microorganisms, offering opportunities for metabolic engineering to enhance shikimic acid and its branched products' production in microorganisms (Wu et al., 2022). Different strategies can be applied to improve the production of compounds of interest, including plant cell culture and gene expression modification (Popova et al., 2021). Metabolic engineering has been used to enhance biosynthetic pathways in plants, extending existing routes or introducing new ones to obtain novel compounds (Hidalgo et al., 2017).

The amylose content of starch is increased after enzymatic modification, forming tightly packed crystallites with digestion resistance after thermal treatment and retrogradation (Sinhmar et al., 2022). The use of plant systems as factories for recombinant protein production has become a prominent alternative for pharmaceutical industries due to their high potential for protein accumulation (Habibi et al., 2017). For the production of recombinant proteins, plants provide a promising alternative platform to conventional cell culture-based systems (Fujiuchi et al., 2015).

Genetic engineering ensures that the plants act as reliable and consistent bioreactors for drug production throughout the duration of the mission.

Personalized genetic modifications are also implemented in pharmaceutical plant platforms for long-range spacecraft missions. These modifications tailor the plants' genetic makeup to accommodate the specific pharmaceutical needs of individual astronauts. Personalized genetic adjustments ensure that the pharmaceutical plant platforms can produce drugs and therapeutic agents that are tailored to the unique physiological characteristics and medical requirements of each crew member.

The use of food plants as pharmaceutical platforms through genetic manipulation is a pioneering approach in space research. Biosensors enhance the functionality of these platforms, enabling real-time monitoring and analysis of biological information. Regenerative medicine strategies support tissue repair and regeneration in space. Genetic engineering and personalized genetic modifications ensure reliable and personalized drug production in long-range spacecraft missions, highlighting the versatility and potential of biotechnology in space exploration.

Genetically modified food plants with DNA damage correction capabilities represent a significant advancement in space research. These plants are engineered to possess mechanisms for self-repairing DNA damage, ensuring genomic stability and functionality in space environments. This genetic modification is particularly important for maintaining the integrity of the plant's genetic material, which can be vulnerable to radiation and other space-related stressors.

Metagenomics is a valuable tool for studying genetic material directly from environmental samples in space habitats. This approach allows for the comprehensive analysis of microbial communities and genetic diversity within closed ecosystems. By examining the genetic material of microorganisms in the spacecraft environment, researchers can gain insights into the interactions between genetically modified plants and the microbial ecosystem, facilitating the optimization of cultivation conditions.

Neuroprosthetics, artificial devices designed to replace or enhance nervous system function, have applications in space research. These devices can be utilized to interface with genetically modified plants, enabling real-time monitoring and control of their DNA repair mechanisms and overall health. Neuroprosthetics offer a means of enhancing the adaptability and resilience of plants in space habitats.

Microorganisms play a crucial role in supporting genetically modified plants for long-range spacecraft missions. These microorganisms are genetically modified to perform specific functions, such as nutrient cycling and waste management, to create closed-loop ecosystems within the spacecraft. Genetically engineered microorganisms enhance the sustainability of plant cultivation by efficiently recycling nutrients and contributing to the overall stability of the habitat.

Closed cultivation systems are essential for long-range spacecraft missions, and genetically modified plants are designed to thrive in these closed environments. These plants are equipped with genetic modifications that optimize resource utilization, water efficiency, and waste management. Closed cultivation systems ensure that plants can provide a consistent source of food and oxygen while minimizing resource consumption, contributing to the self-sufficiency of space habitats.

In summary, genetically modified food plants with DNA damage correction capabilities are a significant breakthrough in space research, ensuring genomic stability in space environments. Metagenomics allows for the study of microbial communities in closed ecosystems. Neuroprosthetics enable real-time monitoring of genetically modified plants. Genetically engineered microorganisms support plant cultivation in closed-loop ecosystems, and closed cultivation systems optimize resource utilization in long-range spacecraft

missions. These advancements demonstrate the interdisciplinary approach to space biotechnology for sustainable space exploration.

Environmental monitoring systems are essential in ensuring optimal conditions for space cultivation. Synthetic coral reefs serve as artificial structures supporting marine ecosystems in space habitats, enhancing biodiversity and nutrient recycling. The Crispr-Chip technology integrates CRISPR with microfluidics for precise genetic analysis, enabling real-time monitoring of plant health and performance.

Genetically modified plants with enhanced radiation resistance are critical for long-range spacecraft missions. These plants are engineered to withstand space radiation, maintaining genetic stability and minimizing DNA damage. Biomimetic genetic modifications enable plants to mimic nature's strategies for survival, enhancing their adaptability and resilience in challenging space environments.

Synthetic coral reefs are integral to space habitats, providing structural support for aquatic ecosystems and promoting sustainable marine life. These artificial reefs mimic natural coral formations and enhance biodiversity by offering shelter and food sources for marine organisms.

The Crispr-Chip technology combines CRISPR-based genetic modification with microfluidics, enabling the precise analysis of plant genetics in space. This technology allows for real-time monitoring of genetic modifications, ensuring the intended genetic traits are maintained and optimized for space cultivation.

Resistance to radiation is a critical genetic modification for plants in long-range spacecraft missions. Genetically modified plants are engineered to withstand the damaging effects of space radiation, preserving their genetic integrity and overall health.

Biomimetic genetic modifications in plants aim to replicate natural survival mechanisms by harnessing the sophisticated mechanisms of gene regulation that plants have developed to ensure their survival upon environmental fluctuations (Thiebaut & Hemerly, 2019). These modifications induce multiple physiological and biochemical alterations in transformed plants, activating secondary metabolic processes and enhancing the plant's response to abiotic and biotic stresses (Scalabrin et al., 2020). Furthermore, the

biomimetic investigation of plants, specifically CAM (Crassulacean Acid Metabolism) plants, illustrates how CO₂ may be converted and stored, providing insights into natural survival mechanisms that can be replicated through genetic modifications (Redgard & Roodt, 2021).

Genetically modified plants have been shown to confer higher resistance against various kinds of stresses, indicating the potential of biomimetic genetic modifications in enhancing plant survival mechanisms (Scalabrin et al., 2015). Additionally, the genetic engineering of plants can be useful for studying and characterizing how gene networks for abiotic stress tolerance interact and perform under a variety of conditions, further emphasizing the potential of biomimetic strategies in replicating natural survival mechanisms in plants (Kumar et al., 2022).

The survival of plants under various stress conditions is highly dependent on the regulation of stress-responsive genes and epigenetic mechanisms, highlighting the importance of epigenetic regulation in the adaptation and stress responses of plants (Priyanka et al., 2021). Furthermore, the genetic variation in plant cells shares biochemical features with off-target modifications, emphasizing the need to understand unintended effects in genome editing applications for plant survival mechanisms (Troadek & Pages, 2019).

Plants must survive under ever-changing environmental conditions characterized by variations in a lot of abiotic stresses, such as salt and cold, and genetic manipulation, based on heterologous gene expression, and natural/induced diversity could be exploited for this aim (Fan, 2019). Moreover, the genetic architecture of plant response to combinatorial stress has not been fully investigated, indicating the potential for biomimetic genetic modifications to enhance combined biotic and abiotic stress resistance in plants (Kissoudis et al., 2015). These genetic alterations enable plants to adapt to space environments by mimicking traits found in nature, ensuring their resilience and ability to thrive in the challenging conditions of long-duration space missions.

Environmental monitoring systems are vital for space cultivation. Synthetic coral reefs support marine ecosystems, and Crispr-Chip technology enables genetic analysis. Genetically modified plants with radiation resistance

and biomimetic traits enhance adaptability in space environments, contributing to the sustainability of long-range spacecraft missions.

Genetic enhancement for vertical agriculture represents a pivotal advancement, enabling the cultivation of nutrient-dense crops in confined spaces. This technology leverages genetic modification to optimize crop traits such as growth rate, yield, and nutritional content, ensuring efficient food production in vertical farming systems.

Regenerative medicine plays a complementary role in the context of space exploration, aiming to stimulate the human body's innate ability to repair and regenerate tissues. This is particularly significant for astronauts facing potential tissue damage due to extended space missions. Regenerative medicine strategies can enhance tissue repair and recovery in space environments.

Neural interface technology is another cutting-edge development that holds promise for space exploration. It involves connecting machines directly to the human brain, enabling communication or control of devices and systems. This technology enhances astronauts' ability to interact with spacecraft equipment and conduct tasks more efficiently in extraterrestrial environments.

Genetically modified plants for long-range spacecraft missions are adapted to thrive in extraterrestrial environments. These plants undergo genetic modifications that improve their resilience to space-related stressors, such as radiation and microgravity. They play a crucial role in providing a sustainable source of food and oxygen for astronauts during extended space journeys.

Furthermore, strategies for space agriculture involve the genetic modification of plants to optimize resource utilization and enhance nutrient absorption in closed-loop ecosystems. These genetically engineered plants contribute to the self-sufficiency and sustainability of space habitats, ensuring a consistent food supply for astronauts.

Genetic enhancement for vertical agriculture is pivotal for efficient food production in confined spaces. Regenerative medicine supports tissue repair in space, while neural interface technology enhances human-machine interaction. Genetically modified plants for extraterrestrial environments and space agriculture strategies are essential components of long-range spacecraft missions, ensuring sustainability and self-sufficiency in space exploration.

Genetically enhanced plants serve as valuable tools for system purification in orbital environments. Through genetic modifications, these plants are designed to possess capabilities that enable them to efficiently remove contaminants from the atmosphere and water systems in spacecraft, contributing to the overall sustainability of life support systems.

Non-invasive brain stimulation techniques, such as transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) and transcranial electrical stimulation (TES), play a crucial role in space research. These methods allow for the modulation of brain activity without the need for surgical intervention. They are employed to investigate and address cognitive and neurological effects experienced by astronauts during space missions, enhancing our understanding of the impact of space environments on brain function.

CRISPR-Cas9 technology is a powerful genome editing tool that offers precise modification of DNA. In the context of space exploration, CRISPR-Cas9 is utilized for genetic modifications in plants, ensuring the development of crops with desired traits such as increased resistance to space-related stressors and enhanced nutrient absorption.

Genetically modified plants are also engineered for the production of phytochemicals, such as antioxidants and secondary metabolites, in long-range spacecraft missions. These bioactive compounds have various applications, including supporting astronaut health by mitigating the effects of space radiation and oxidative stress, as well as enhancing the nutritional value of space diets.

Furthermore, genetically modified plants designed for DNA repair mechanisms contribute to the overall genetic stability and health of crops during extended space travel. These modifications ensure that the plants can effectively address DNA damage caused by space radiation and other stressors, maintaining their genetic integrity and functionality.

Genetically enhanced plants play a crucial role in system purification in orbital environments. Non-invasive brain stimulation techniques aid in studying brain function in space. CRISPR-Cas9 technology enables precise genetic modifications, and genetically modified plants produce phytochemicals and support DNA repair in long-range spacecraft missions. These advancements demonstrate the versatility and potential of biotechnology in space exploration.

3. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The convergence of biotechnology and space exploration has ushered in a new era of possibilities, propelling our understanding of sustainable space journeys to unprecedented heights. In our exploration of the groundbreaking concepts and advancements discussed in this article, several key takeaways and considerations emerge.

Firstly, the development of food plants engineered as pharmaceutical platforms signifies a monumental leap in ensuring the health and well-being of astronauts during long-range spacecraft missions. Genetic modifications have transformed these plants into reliable bioreactors, offering a self-sufficient source of vital drugs and therapeutic compounds. The ability to tailor these modifications to individual astronauts' needs underscores the potential for personalized medicine in space.

Biosensors, as critical components of this biotechnology, provide real-time monitoring and analysis, affording precise control over drug production and overall plant health. Their integration enhances the functionality and efficiency of pharmaceutical plant platforms, safeguarding both astronauts and mission success.

The incorporation of regenerative medicine strategies offers an added layer of support for astronauts facing tissue damage and healing challenges in space. By stimulating and enhancing tissue regeneration, we ensure the resilience and adaptability of the human body during extended missions.

Genetic engineering techniques, coupled with DNA repair capabilities, are vital for the survival and functionality of genetically modified plants in space environments. These modifications are not only critical for pharmaceutical production but also for the long-term sustainability of closed-loop ecosystems within spacecraft.

Metagenomics provides a holistic view of microbial communities in space habitats, shedding light on complex interactions and nutrient cycling. This knowledge is invaluable for optimizing cultivation conditions and ecosystem stability.

Neuroprosthetics enable real-time monitoring and control of plant health, offering a means of enhancing adaptability in space habitats. These artificial interfaces bridge the gap between humans and biotechnological systems, maximizing the potential of plant-based bioreactors.

Genetically engineered microorganisms further contribute to ecosystem sustainability, efficiently recycling nutrients and minimizing waste. Their role in creating closed-loop ecosystems cannot be understated, as they bolster the overall stability of space habitats.

Closed cultivation systems, optimized through genetic modifications, ensure efficient resource utilization, water conservation, and minimal waste generation. These systems play a pivotal role in the self-sufficiency and long-term viability of space missions.

In conclusion, the interdisciplinary approach to space biotechnology presented in this article underscores the remarkable potential of genetic engineering, regenerative medicine, and advanced technologies in ensuring sustainable space exploration. As we venture further into the cosmos, the fusion of biology and technology promises not only to revolutionize space research but also to redefine our understanding of what is possible beyond Earth's boundaries. The future of space exploration is, indeed, fertile ground for innovative solutions and transformative discoveries.

REFERENCES

- Ayan, A., Meriç, S., Gümüş, T., & Atak, Ç. (2022). Next generation of transgenic plants: from farming to pharming.. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.102004>
- Chen, Y., Ning, Y., Yao, S., Zhuang, J., Fu, Z., Ma, J., ... & Xia, T. (2021). cshct-mediated lignin synthesis pathway involved in the response of tea plants to biotic and abiotic stresses. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 69(35), 10069-10081. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.1c02771>
- Chung, Y., Church, D., Koellhoffer, E., Osota, E., Shukla, S., Rybicki, E., ... & Steinmetz, N. (2021). Integrating plant molecular farming and materials research for next-generation vaccines. *Nature Reviews Materials*, 7(5), 372-388. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41578-021-00399-5>
- Daniell, H., Jin, S., Zhu, X., Gitzendanner, M., Soltis, D., & Soltis, P. (2021). Green giant—a tiny chloroplast genome with mighty power to produce high-value proteins: history and phylogeny. *Plant Biotechnology Journal*, 19(3), 430-447. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pbi.13556>
- Eidenberger, L., Kogelmann, B., & Steinkellner, H. (2023). Plant-based biopharmaceutical engineering. *Nature Reviews Bioengineering*, 1(6), 426-439. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44222-023-00044-6>
- Fan, C. (2019). Genetic mechanisms of salt stress responses in halophytes. *Plant Signaling & Behavior*, 15(1), 1704528. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15592324.2019.1704528>
- Fan, G., Dundas, C., Graham, A., Lynd, N., & Keitz, B. (2018). *shewanella oneidensis* as a living electrode for controlled radical polymerization. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(18), 4559-4564. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1800869115>
- Fujiuchi, N., Matsuda, R., Matoba, N., & Fujiwara, K. (2015). Removal of bacterial suspension water occupying the intercellular space of detached leaves after agroinfiltration improves the yield of recombinant hemagglutinin in a *nicotiana benthamiana* transient gene expression system. *Biotechnology and Bioengineering*, 113(4), 901-906. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bit.25854>
- Goel, N., Dhaliwal, I., Sharma, M., Kumar, R., & Kaushik, P. (2021). Epigenetics: a key to comprehending biotic and abiotic stress tolerance in family poaceae.. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202107.0135.v1>

<p>Habibi, P., Daniell, H., Soccol, C., & Grossi-de-Sá, M. (2019). The potential of plant systems to break the hiv-tb link. <i>Plant Biotechnology Journal</i>, 17(10), 1868-1891. https://doi.org/10.1111/pbi.13110</p>
<p>Habibi, P., Prado, G., Pelegrini, P., Hefferon, K., Soccol, C., & Grossi-de-Sá, M. (2017). Optimization of inside and outside factors to improve recombinant protein yield in plant. <i>Plant Cell Tissue and Organ Culture (Pctoc)</i>, 130(3), 449-467. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11240-017-1240-5</p>
<p>Hidalgo, D., Georgiev, M., Marchev, A., Bru-Martínez, R., Cusido, R., Corchete, P., ... & Palazon, J. (2017). Tailoring tobacco hairy root metabolism for the production of stilbenes. <i>Scientific Reports</i>, 7(1). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-18330-w</p>
<p>Kissoudis, C., Chowdhury, R., Heusden, S., Wiel, C., Finkers, R., Visser, R., ... & Linden, G. (2015). Combined biotic and abiotic stress resistance in tomato. <i>Euphytica</i>, 202(2), 317-332. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10681-015-1363-x</p>
<p>Kumar, G., Kumar, P., Choudhary, S., Kosser, R., Khanday, D., Choudhary, S., ... & Behera, T. (2022). Biomimetic strategies for developing abiotic stress-tolerant tomato cultivars: an overview. <i>Plants</i>, 12(1), 86. https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12010086</p>
<p>Lu, X., Tang, K., & Li, P. (2016). Plant metabolic engineering strategies for the production of pharmaceutical terpenoids. <i>Frontiers in Plant Science</i>, 7. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2016.01647</p>
<p>Marchev, A., Yordanova, Z., & Georgiev, M. (2020). Green (cell) factories for advanced production of plant secondary metabolites. <i>Critical Reviews in Biotechnology</i>, 40(4), 443-458. https://doi.org/10.1080/07388551.2020.1731414</p>
<p>Marsafari, M., Samizadeh, H., Rabiei, B., Mehrabi, A., Koffas, M., & Xu, P. (2020). Biotechnological production of flavonoids: an update on plant metabolic engineering, microbial host selection, and genetically encoded biosensors. <i>Biotechnology Journal</i>, 15(8). https://doi.org/10.1002/biot.201900432</p>
<p>McNulty, M., Xiong, Y., Yates, K., Karuppanan, K., Hilzinger, J., Berliner, A., ... & McDonald, K. (2020). Molecular pharming to support human life on the moon, mars, and beyond.. https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202009.0086.v1</p>

<p>Pan, Y., Yoon, S., Sun, J., Huang, Z., Lee, C., Allen, M., ... & Wang, Y. (2018). Mechanogenetics for the remote and noninvasive control of cancer immunotherapy. <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences</i>, 115(5), 992-997. https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1714900115</p>
<p>Popova, A., Mihaylova, D., & Spasov, A. (2021). Plant-based remedies with reference to respiratory diseases – a review. <i>The Open Biotechnology Journal</i>, 15(1), 46-58. https://doi.org/10.2174/1874434602015010046</p>
<p>Redgard, S. and Roodt, A. (2021). Nucleophile-assisted carbon dioxide fixation for a cleaner environment. <i>Acta Crystallographica Section a Foundations and Advances</i>, 77(a2), C1029-C1029. https://doi.org/10.1107/s0108767321086724</p>
<p>Scalabrin, E., Radaelli, M., & Capodaglio, G. (2020). Effects of water deficit and heat stress on nicotiana langsdorffii metabolomic pattern modified by insertion of rold gene from agrobacterium rhizogenes. <i>Metabolites</i>, 10(8), 310. https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo10080310</p>
<p>Scalabrin, E., Radaelli, M., Rizzato, G., Bogani, P., Buiatti, M., Gambaro, A., ... & Capodaglio, G. (2015). Metabolomic analysis of wild and transgenic nicotiana langsdorffii plants exposed to abiotic stresses: unraveling metabolic responses. <i>Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry</i>, 407(21), 6357-6368. https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-015-8770-7</p>
<p>Shanmugaraj, B., Bulaon, C., & Phoolcharoen, W. (2020). Plant molecular farming: a viable platform for recombinant biopharmaceutical production. <i>Plants</i>, 9(7), 842. https://doi.org/10.3390/plants9070842</p>
<p>Sinhmar, A., Pathera, A., Sharma, S., Nehra, M., Thory, R., & Nain, V. (2022). Impact of various modification methods on physicochemical and functional properties of starch: a review. <i>Starch - Stärke</i>, 75(1-2). https://doi.org/10.1002/star.202200117</p>
<p>Thiebaut, F. and Hemerly, A. (2019). A role for epigenetic regulation in the adaptation and stress responses of non-model plants. <i>Frontiers in Plant Science</i>, 10. https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2019.00246</p>
<p>Timoneda, A., Sheehan, H., Feng, T., Lopez-Nieves, S., & Maéda, H. (2018). Redirecting primary metabolism to boost production of tyrosine-derived specialised metabolites in planta. <i>Scientific Reports</i>, 8(1). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-33742-y</p>

Troadec, M. and Pages, J. (2019). Where are we with unintended effects in genome editing applications from dna to phenotype: focus on plant applications. *Transgenic Research*, 28(S2), 125-133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11248-019-00146-1>

Tschofen, M., Knopp, D., Hood, E., & Stoger, E. (2016). Plant molecular farming: much more than medicines. *Annual Review of Analytical Chemistry*, 9(1), 271-294. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anchem-071015-041706>

Uysal, F., Sönmez, R., & İşleyen, S. (2021). A graphical processing unit-based parallel hybrid genetic algorithm for resource-constrained multi-project scheduling problem. *Concurrency and Computation Practice and Experience*, 33(16). <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.6266>

Wilbanks, B., Layton, D., Garcia, S., & Trinh, C. (2017). A prototype for modular cell engineering. *Acs Synthetic Biology*, 7(1), 187-199. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssynbio.7b00269>

Wu, S., Chen, W., Lu, S., Zhang, H., & Yin, L. (2022). Metabolic engineering of shikimic acid biosynthesis pathway for the production of shikimic acid and its branched products in microorganisms: advances and prospects. *Molecules*, 27(15), 4779. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27154779>